

Studies in Terpenes. Part XI. A Contribution to the Understanding of the Diels-Alder Reaction of 3-Carene with Maleic Anhydride

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Three types of transformations, viz., isomerisation, diene synthesis, and aromatisation, take place when 3-carene is allowed to react with maleic anhydride.

Isomerisation leads to α -terpinene, terpinolene, dipentene, and *m*-isomers.

Addition of maleic anhydride to the intermediate, α -phellandrene, affords the racemic adduct as observed by Hultzsch³. The crude mixture of adducts undergoes thermal decomposition to provide *p*-cymene, *m*-cymene, and succinic anhydride, indicating presence of condensation products derived from *p*- and *m*-menthadienes.

Aromatisation to cymenes constitutes a superficial side reaction. The benzenoids arise either by decomposition of adducts or by hydrogen transfer involving menthadienes.

A quick and sensitive method for the preparation of α -terpinene nitrosite is described.

By refluxing the compound formulated as (I), but incorrectly referred to as 3-carene, with maleic anhydride, Diels *et al.*^{1,2a} obtained an adduct which furnished a dicarboxylic acid, different from the corresponding acid of α -terpinene, as shown by mixed m.p. Later, Hultzsch³ obtained from 3-carene (II) an adduct which afforded an optically active dicarboxylic acid. This acid was not identical with the one derived from terpinolene adduct.

Hultzsch³ was also able to isolate the adduct of ($\pm$)- α -phellandrene. These reactions have been briefly and critically discussed by Norton⁴ and Goodway and West⁵. ~~The~~ latter authors have pointed out the desirability of investigating further the behaviour of 3-carene towards maleic anhydride. This has prompted us, in our

1. *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1183.

2a. Simonsen, "The Terpenes", 2nd ed., Vol. II, Cambridge University Press, 1957, p. 75.

2b. *Ibid.*, p. 69.

3. *Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1173.

4. *Chem. Rev.*, 1942, 31, 310.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 702.

studies on the transformations of mono- and bicyclic terpenes with maleic anhydride, to direct our attention on 3-carene. The results of the present investigation are summarised in Table I.

Reaction (a), which was a repetition of the work of Diels *et al.*¹ on 3-carene, afforded α -terpinene, dipentene, *m*-isomers, *p*- and *m*-cymenes, and succinic anhydride. Moreover, pyrolysis of the crude adduct resulted in *p*- and *m*-cymenes and succinic anhydride. The succinic anhydride was recovered as the acid.

A different picture was revealed in the 1 hr.-interaction of 3-carene in acetone with maleic anhydride (reaction b)⁶. Under these mild conditions, two other isomers could be identified, viz., α -phellandrene as its racemic adduct and terpinolene. *m*-Isomers and cymenes were also present but not α -terpinene and dipentene. Also, as shown by reaction (c), there was no difference in the transformation of 3-carene when heated with maleic anhydride for 2 hrs. at $75^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ in absence of acetone as solvent.

Reaction (d), conducted in a closed vessel, afforded terpinolene, *m*-isomers, and cymenes. α -Phellandrene and dipentene could not be detected. In the 6 hr.-run (reaction e), however, α -terpinene was formed in addition to terpinolene, *m*-isomers, and cymenes.

Finally in reaction (f), in which 3-carene was kept in contact with powdered maleic anhydride at room temperature ($25-30^\circ$) for 4 days, apparently very little change was noticed⁷.

The above results lead to the general fact that the cyclopropane ring of 3-carene has suffered a two-way cleavage to provide *para*- and *meta*- derivatives.

Of the *p*-isomers, terpinolene is met with most frequently; this is followed by α -phellandrene, α -terpinene, and then dipentene. It is significant that neither α -terpinene nor dipentene was present when terpinolene and α -phellandrene occurred concurrently. Terpinolene and α -phellandrene are therefore primary isomerisation products. This is in agreement with the isomerisation scheme proposed by Lyubarskii⁸ and Brooks⁹. Moreover, the isolation of the racemic α -phellandrene adduct confirms the observation of Hultsch³.

In 3-carene, the cyclopropane ring is not in conjugation with the double bond and therefore the production of α -phellandrene adduct is not parallel to the formation of the same adduct from α -thujene, which is a clear example of a 'forced' diene synthesis, involving a double bond in conjugation with a 3-membered ring.¹⁰

A unique observation is that dipentene is formed only in reaction (a), done under conditions prescribed by Diels *et al.*¹. Furthermore, this reaction is conspicuous by absence of terpinolene in the products. It is probable that dipentene is formed at the expense of

6. Cf. Birch, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1937, 71, 54.

7. Cf. Gireeson, "Isomerisation Studies in Mono- and Bicyclic Terpenes. A Contribution to the Chemistry of 3-Carene",—M.Sc. Thesis, Madras University, 1960, p. 25.

8. *Zhur. Prikl. Khim.*, 1931, 4, 361.

9. "The Chemistry of Nonbenzenoid Hydrocarbons", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, N. Y., 1950, p. 409.

10. Gascogne, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1941, 74, 359.

terpinolene. Whether dipentene and terpinolene are mutually interconvertible with maleic anhydride is under investigation.

Lastly, γ -terpinene could not be detected in any of these reactions. Most probably, this terpene might have isomerised to α -terpinene under the influence of maleic anhydride¹⁰.

As regards *m*-isomers, Wallach's colour test¹¹⁻¹² with acetic anhydride-sulphuric acid reagents on steam-volatile oil from reaction mixture indicates that rearrangement of 3-carene to *m*-isomers has taken place. Although the physico-chemical characterisation of *m*-isomers has not been carried out, the expulsion of *m*-cymene on pyrolysis of adduct mixture (reaction a) suggests that *m*-isomers, capable of entering into diene synthesis, are formed from 3-carene.

From the foregoing discussion, it emerges that in presence of maleic anhydride, 3-carene displays pronounced tendency to undergo isomerisation and that the isomerisation step precedes condensation. The suppression of diene reaction in favour of isomerisation has been demonstrated under various experimental conditions. Evidently, the nature of the adducts that originate from 3-carene is dictated by the mode of rearrangement of the terpene into products capable of adding maleic anhydride. Of the *p*-isomers, α -phellandrene, 3,8(9)-*p*-menthadiene, and α -terpinene can directly incorporate maleic anhydride, but only α -phellandrene could be isolated as its adduct. γ -Terpinene was identified by preparation of its nitrosite, but from the complex mixture of adducts, the fractional crystallisation of the adducts corresponding to this and 3,8(9)-*p*-menthadiene was not successful. Moreover, we could not isolate by our analytical technique either the adducts or dicarboxylic acids, described by Diels *et al.*¹ or Hultzsch². This aspect of the problem we propose to investigate later. Also evidence is accumulating in this laboratory to show that some of the *m*-isomers can condense with maleic anhydride. In other words, in reactions of 3-carene with maleic anhydride, we should expect adducts belonging to both *p*- and *m*-isomers. The fact that pyrolysis of the crude adduct isolated from the reaction mixture (a) furnishes *p*- and *m*-cymenes justifies the above assumption. These aromatics arise by decomposition of the adducts with expulsion of succinic anhydride¹³ and by hydrogen-transfer reactions¹⁴.

Incidentally, recommended methods¹⁵ for preparation of α -terpinene nitrosite gave only oily products. The procedure now described is extremely sensitive, quick, and capable of detecting even 0.5 ml or less of α -terpinene. Crude nitrosite of m.p. $\approx 150^\circ$ was obtained; a single recrystallisation raised the m.p. to 155° .

In conclusion, it can be stated that 3-carene can furnish only a mixture of adducts on interaction with maleic anhydride. It is clearly desirable to obtain further data on the transformations of various other mono- and bicyclic terpenes under the influence of

11. Wallach, *Annalen*, 1886, 230, 240; 1887, 239, 4.

12. Bardyshev, *Doklady Akad. Nauk. SSSR.*, 1953, 90, (6), 1035.

13. Litmann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 586; *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1936, 28, 1150.

14. Verghese *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, 16B, 363; Ipatieff *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 694; Ipatieff and Pines, U. S. P. 2,431,758/1947; 2,420,749/1947; Kuryndin, *Zhur. Prikl. Khim.*, 1948, 21, 273.

15. Wallach, *Annalen*, 1887, 239, 35; Guenther, "The Essential Oils", Vol. II, D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., N.Y. 1962, pp. 36, 785.

maleic anhydride in order to postulate a comprehensive reaction mechanism. We are presently investigating the reaction of a variety of terpenes with maleic anhydride as well as maleic acid which will be the subject of future reports.

EXPERIMENTAL*

3-Carene was prepared by careful three-fold fractionation of Indian turpentine oil of *Pinus longifolia* (Roxb.) (Bareilly first quality.) through a Quickfit column. All fractions with refractive index in the range n_D^{20} 1.4728—1.4731 were combined and refractionated in a Todd Precise Fractionation Assembly, using 90 cm/25 mm column, packed with single turn glass helices, at a reflux ratio of 25:1. The 3-carene, thus obtained, had the following constants: b.p. 169-71°/740 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4731; d_4^{20} 0.8617; m.p. of nitrosate, 147.5° (decomp.) (lit. value: 147.5°)^{16,17a,b}.

Maleic anhydride was of Eastman Kodak white label grade. All other chemicals were either AnalaR or of Chemically Pure grade.

(A) Oil

Volatile components of the reaction mixture were removed by steam distillation and dried.

(i). *Wallach's test*¹¹⁻¹² on this oil was performed as follows: The oil (3 drops) in acetic anhydride was added, followed by a drop of H₂SO₄ (conc.). A methylene blue coloration indicated the presence of *m*-isomers.

The oil was subjected to distillation in the Todd Precise Fractionation Assembly. The "cuts" were analysed by chemical means for presence of various hydrocarbons. Saturates were isolated directly, using a portion of the steam-volatile oil.

(ii). *Identification*: (a) *3-Carene*.—3-Carene was recognised by the formation of the nitrosate, m.p. 147.5° (decomp.)^{17a,b}, following essentially the method of Simonsen¹⁶. Recrystallisation of the crude nitrosate (m.p. $\approx$ 135°), however, was done by dissolving in chloroform and precipitating with cold methanol.

(b) *α -Terpinene: A New Method for the Preparation of α -Terpinene Nitrosite*.—To a solution of the oil (3 ml) in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and absolute ethanol (5 ml) was added dropwise sodium nitrite (2g. in 3 ml of water), followed by petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°, 6ml). The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-salt bath. Crystals began to appear in about 10 mins. For completion, the reaction mixture was set aside for 24 hrs. in the refrigerator. The crystals formed were collected by filtration and the filtrate on ~~distilled~~ with water (5 ml) afforded the same solid material. These two crops were washed with petroleum ether and then recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The analytical sample obtained melted at 155°¹³, not depressed by an authentic sample.

*All melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. Yields of oils reported are after drying over Drierite.

16. Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 570.

TABLE I

Analytical data of steam-volatile reaction products.

Reaction:	b*		o**		d*		e*			
	Yield.	n _D ²⁰ .	Yield.	n _D ²⁰ .	Yield.	n _D ²⁰ .	Yield.	n _D ²⁰ .		
Wt. of oil (fractionated, (g.): 25	34	738.5	85	737	25	739.3	34	739		
Pressure (mm):	738.4									
Fraction No.	Yield.	n _D ²⁰ .	Compds. identified.	Yield.	n _D ²⁰ .	Compds. identified.	Yield.	n _D ²⁰ .		
B.P.	Compds. identified.			Compds. identified.			Compds. identified.			
1.	162-65°	0.9	1.4743	Nil	..	..	..	..		
2.	165-68°	1.2	1.4805	Nil	..	..	..	..		
3.	168-71°	2.7	1.4785	Nil	25.8g.	1.4729	3-Carene	17.4g.	1.4729	3-Carene
4.	171-73°	4.4	1.4819	α-Terpinene	1.3	1.4730	3-Carene	3.8	1.4730	3-Carene
5.	173-76°	5.1	1.4809	α-Terpinene	1.5	1.4770	Nil	1.0	1.4811	Nil
6.	175-78°	3.6	1.4831	α-Terpinene Dipentene	0.85	1.4647	Nil	0.85	1.4740	α-Terpinene
7.	178-81°	..	..	..	0.85	1.4841	Nil	0.3	1.4656	Nil
8.	181-88°	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
9.	Residue, steam distilled	0.9	1.5011	Nil	..	..	..	..	..	..
p-Cymene (%)	12.4				1.1	1.4653	Terpinolene	1.8	1.4880	Terpinolene
m-Cymene (%)	23.5				0.5	1.4697	Terpinolene	1.1	1.4664	Nil
					Traces		Traces		2.2	
					Traces		Traces		6.1	

*Fractionation with 80 cm/5 mm column, Monel spiral packing, at a reflux ratio 25:1.

**Fractionation with 90 cm/12 mm column, Pyrex brand glass helices packing, at a reflux ratio 50:1.

(c) *Terpinolene and Dipentene*.—These monocyclics were identified *via* tetrabromides, using the bromination procedure described earlier¹⁷. Crude dipentene tetrabromide was recrystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol. The m.p. of 116°¹⁸ and 125°¹⁹ showed no depression on admixture with genuine samples of terpinolene and dipentene tetrabromides, respectively.

(iii). *Cymenes (m- & p-)*.—A portion of the oil was stirred (magnetically) for 6 hrs. with twice its volume of ice-cold 80% H₂SO₄²⁰. The unaffected oil was recovered and agitated (magnetically) for 5 mins., twice, with H₂SO₄ (conc., cold, 10% by volume)²¹. The saturates were isolated in the usual manner, washed with water, basified with 10% NaOH (aq.), steam distilled, and dried. Cymenes were estimated in the saturates by oxidation to terephthalic and isophthalic acids on the lines indicated by Xavier *et al.*²². The percentages in steam-volatile reaction products obtained by them are recorded in Table I. Terephthalic and isophthalic acids were further converted into dimethyl terephthalate²³ of m.p. 140-41° and dimethyl isophthalate²⁴ of m.p. 64-65°; these m.p.'s were not depressed when mixed with authentic samples of dimethyl terephthalate and dimethyl isophthalate, respectively.

(B) Isolation of (±)- α -Phellandrene Adduct

The residue left after steam distilling the original reaction mixture was washed repeatedly with water and taken up in ether ($\approx$ 30 ml). The ether phase was separated and to this was added petroleum ether ($\approx$ 30 ml). The solution was allowed to stand in an ice-salt bath for 3 hrs. The solids crystallised were collected, washed with petroleum ether, and dried over a porous plate. The m.p.^{5,25} of the product, 93°, was unchanged on admixture with an authentic sample of (±)- α -phellandrene-maleic anhydride adduct.

Reactions of 3-Carene with Maleic Anhydride

Reaction (a).—3-Carene (27.2 g., 0.2M) and maleic anhydride (20 g., 0.2M) were charged to a 2-necked flask, equipped with thermometer and reflux condenser carrying a calcium chloride guard tube, and heated together on a Glas-col heating mantle for 6 hrs. Refluxing started at 165° and the temperature rose to 265° during the course of about 3½ hrs. and remained steady for the rest of the period. The white solid in the condenser was washed down with water and the reaction mixture steam distilled. The volatile oil obtained was rendered alkaline with aqueous NaOH and again steam distilled (yield 4.3 g., b.p. 162-78°/738.4 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4859). The material left after expelling the oil from the original reaction mixture was extracted with ether. The ether and aqueous phases were separately collected.

17. Verghese, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 260.

18. Wallach, *Annalen* 1885, **227**, 283.

19. Wallach, *ibid.*, 1893, **275**, 103.

20. Verghese and Yeddapanalli, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, **12B**, 121.

21. Pines *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4872.

22. *Curr. Sci.*, 1953, **22**, 112; Yeddapanalli *et al.*, "The Symposium on Contact Catalysis", *Bull. Natl. Inst. Sci., India*, 1959, No. 12, 179.

23. Huntress and Mulliken, "Identification of Pure Organic Compounds", Order I, Chapman & Hall Ltd., London, 1946, p. 178.

24. Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1921.

25. Birch, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1937, **71**, 261; Goodway and West, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1937, **56**, 472T; see also references 3 & 10.

The ether solution was washed with water, dried, and evaporated to dryness. An amber-coloured viscous residue (A) was obtained (yield 38.1 g.). Evaporation of the combined aqueous extracts on a water bath gave a slightly sticky solid (B) (yield 2.5 g.). The reaction was repeated several times to obtain a workable quantity of the volatile oil.

(i) *Oil*.—The analytical data are presented in Table I under reaction (a). From 2.6 g. of fractions (4), (5), and (6), α -terpinene nitrosite was obtained in yields of about 500 mg., 450 mg., and 160 mg. respectively. Fraction (6) (850 mg.) afforded about 40 mg. of dipentene tetrabromide. Fraction (5) and the residue failed to furnish any bromo derivative; *p*- and *m*-cymenes amounted to 12.4% and 23.5% respectively of the steam-volatile reaction product.

(ii) *Residue (A): Thermal Decomposition*.—The residue (11.5 g.) was refluxed on a Glas-col heating mantle for 6 hrs., the mantle temperature being 230-330°. Solids inside the condenser were washed with water into the flask and a current of steam passed in. The volatile portion was rendered alkaline with aqueous NaOH solution and on steam distillation afforded an oil with cymene smell (yield 1.7 g., n_D^{20} 1.4805). Oxidation of this oil afforded 60 mg. of terephthalic acid and 95 mg. of isophthalic acid, indicating thereby presence of *p*- and *m*-cymenes respectively.

The contents in the steam distillation flask were treated with ether. The aqueous and ether layers were separated and the latter was repeatedly washed with water. Aqueous extracts were combined and evaporated on a water bath. About 300 mg. of a solid residue was obtained. This was recrystallised from water. The crystals obtained, when heated at 100° for 12 hrs., gave m.p. of 184°, undepressed by succinic acid.

(iii) *Solid (B)*, when recrystallised from water and heated at 100° for 12 hrs., showed ~~stone~~ and when mixed with succinic acid, m.p. of 184°.

Reaction (b).—3-Carene (51.6 g., 0.38 *M*), maleic anhydride (74.5 g., 0.76 *M*), and acetone (120 ml) were kept together in a closed 500 ml r.b. flask for 1 hour. The acetone from the reaction mixture was expelled by keeping over a boiling water bath. The residue was washed with water and then steam distilled. The volatile oil was processed as in reaction (a) (yield 39.3 g., n_D^{20} 1.4748, b.p. 168-78°/738.5 mm) and the non-volatile residue preserved for further examination.

(i) *Oil*.—In Table I under reaction (b) are recorded the analytical data of the oil. From 1.0 g. of fractions (3) and (4) about 200 mg. of 3-carene nitrosate was obtained. Fractions (5) and (6) did not yield any nitrosite or bromide. Bromination of fraction (9) (850 mg.) afforded about 250 mg. of terpinolene tetrabromide. Cymenes amounted to only traces in the volatile oil.

(ii) *Residue*.—From the residue about 10 mg. of ($\pm$)- α -phellandrene-maleic anhydride adduct was isolated.

Reaction (c).—A mixture of 3-carene (103.2 g., 0.76 *M*) and maleic anhydride (149 g., 1.52 *M*) was heated in a r.b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser carrying a calcium chloride guard tube for 2 hrs. at 75° $\pm$ 2° on a Fisher Hi-Temp Bath. The maleic anhydride melted, but did not mix completely with the oil. At the end of the reaction period, excess of water was added, the oily layer separated, washed with water, and steam distilled. The

volatile oil was worked up as described earlier (yield 88.2 g., n_D^{20} 1.4746, b.p. 168-78°/737 mm). The yellow residue left after removing the oil from the original mixture was washed with water and then further analysed.

(i) *Oil*.—Under reaction (c) in Table I are summarised the analytical data of the oil. Fractions (3) and (4) afforded 3-carene nitrosate. Attempts to prepare nitrosite and bromide derivatives from fractions (5) and (6), respectively, were not successful. From 1.7 g. of the steam-volatile residue, about 1.2 g. of terpinolene tetrabromide was prepared. The volatile oil contained only traces of cymenes.

(ii) *Residue*.—From the residue about 15 mg. of ($\pm$)- α -phellandrene-maleic anhydride adduct was separated.

Reaction (d).—3-Carene (34.4 g., 0.25 *M*) and maleic anhydride (49 g., 0.50 *M*) were heated together in a closed r. b. flask for 2 hrs. at 75° $\pm$ 2° in a Fisher Hi-Temp Bath and the reaction product processed in the usual way (yield of oil 32.5 g., n_D^{20} 1.4745, b.p. 168-78°/730.3 mm).

Oil.—A summary of the results of analyses of the oil is recorded in Table I under reaction (d). Fractions (3) and (4) furnished 3-carene nitrosate. Nitrosite corresponding to α -terpinene could not be obtained from fractions (4), (5), and (6). From fraction (9) (400 mg.) about 30 mg. of terpinolene tetrabromide was prepared. Only traces of cymenes were present in the volatile oil.

Reaction (e).—Reaction (d) was repeated by altering the heating period to 6 hrs. and using a mixture of 3-carene (51.6 g., 0.38 *M*) and maleic anhydride (74.5 g., 0.76 *M*). The yield of oil amounted to 46.2 g. (n_D^{20} 1.4750, b.p. 168-88°/739 mm).

The analytical data on the oil are listed in Table I under reaction (e). Fraction (3) afforded 3-carene nitrosate. Fractions (4), (5), and (6) were tested for α -terpinene. From 600 mg. of each of these fractions about 10 to 15 mg. of α -terpinene nitrosite could be obtained. Fractions (7) and (9) did not yield any bromo derivative. Fraction (8) (1.3 g) gave about 250 mg. of terpinolene tetrabromide. In this reaction, the volatile reaction product contained 2.2% of *p*-cymene and 5.1% of *m*-cymene.

Reaction (f).—Powdered maleic anhydride (49 g., 0.50 *M*) and 3-carene (34.4 g., 0.25 *M*) were kept together in a r. b. flask for 4 days (25-30°) and the product worked up as described in reaction (c); yield of oil, 32.5 g.; n_D^{20} 1.4736; b.p. 168-71°/738 mm.

Fractionation of the oil in the Todd Fractionation Assembly using 90 cm/5 mm column at a reflux ratio of 25:1 gave almost exclusively 3-carene (86.6%, b.p. 168-71°, n_D^{20} 1.4730). The residue when steam distilled gave an oil (yield 1.7 g., n_D^{20} 1.4763) on which no chemical analysis was made.